

Design for analyzing rice ShB epidemiologic processes under secondcontrolled environmental conditions.

Maximum diseased leaf area (DLA): a new parameter for leaf blast (Bl) severity

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Bl disease, caused by *Pyricularia grisea* Sacc., is evaluated in many experiments. Leaf Bl is often assessed three or more times on the same plot within a season. Epidemiological studies require exact disease assessment, which is labor-intensive. The percentage DLA, a parameter commonly used, can be assessed visually with sufficient precision by a well-trained person using standard diagrams.

We analyzed data sets of two experiments in upland rice with the aim to reduce the labor required for disease assessment. Leaf Bl was assessed visually on five fully developed leaves of 20 tillers/plot for 72 plots.

Leaf Bl progress followed a typical pattern (Fig. 1). Depending on meteorological conditions, initial disease symptoms appeared 15-25 d after seeding (DAS) (on Zadoks' scale of growth, stage 15, 20/18, 22), followed by a progressive increase in disease severity. The peak in the progress curve occurred at 40-50 DAS. A steep decrease in severity was

1. Typical pattern of leaf Bl progress.

observed thereafter and an initial low was reached about 70-80 DAS. This pattern was confirmed during several years of field experiments in the Philippines.

Fertilizer application and various upland cultivars (UPLRi-5, C22, Kinandang Patong, and IR47686-6-2-2-1) showed a synchronous disease progress (Fig. 1). A close linear relationship ($r^2 = 0.99$, $n = 72$, based on data range of 0-60% DLA) between the maximum DLA and area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) was observed (Fig. 2). Comparing treatment means for AUDPC and for maximum DLA yielded the same result.

Using the maximum DLA as a parameter for leaf Bl severity proved to be a reliable and practical method in

2. Relation of AUDPC and values of maximum DLA for leaf Bl.

several field experiments. The sensitive response of the disease progress to meteorological conditions—especially at the early vegetative stage when rice plants are extremely susceptible to Bl—requires continuous monitoring of actual disease intensity in control plots. This procedure enables the researcher to predict the time of maximum disease severity.

Weather conditions and cultivar resistance can alter leaf Bl progress. Comparing data from various sites and rice cultures using maximum DLA needs further investigation. Researchers are encouraged to test the parameter under their specific site conditions. ■